

D4.1 Stakeholder learning needs assessment mapped to learning objectives

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QUANTUM summary	QUANTUM aims at developing and implementing a label mechanism that could be ideally adopted in the future HealthData@EU. QUANTUM builds on 5 technical work packages (WP). WP1 conceptualises and provides technical specifications for a data quality, utility, and maturity label. WP2 designs and tests, at small-scale, the label. WP3 implements the labelling mechanism in a number of data holders. WP4 engages the data quality users' community; and, WP5 outreaches other interested parties, including other initiatives building HealthData@EU.
Deliverable abstract	Gap analysis to retrieve stakeholder' training needs and proposal of an educational curriculum
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QUANTUM CONSORTIUM			
#	Short Name	Organisation Name	Country
1	IACS	INSTITUTO ARAGONÉS DE CIENCIAS DE LA SALUD	ES
2	Sciensano	SCIENSANO	BE
3	Health Data Hub	PLATEFORME DES DONNEES DE SANTE	FR
3.1	HOSPICES LYON	HOSPICES CIVILS DE LYON	FR
3.2	HOSP TOULOUSE	CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE TOULOUSE	FR
3.3	CHU Bordeaux	CHU HOPITAUX DE BORDEAUX	FR
4	I-HD	THE EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION THROUGH HEALTH DATA	BE
5	UCSC	UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE	IT
6	BBMRI-ERIC	BIOBANKS AND BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	AT
7	DIGITALEUROPE	DIGITALEUROPE AISBL	BE
8	GÖG	GESUNDHEIT OSTERREICH GMBH	AT
9	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES
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11	EUHA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ALLIANCE	BE
12	AP-HP	ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HOPITAUX DE PARIS	FR
13	VIB	VIB VZW	BE
14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
15	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI
16	THL	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	FI
17	ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	FR
18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
20	ISS	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA	IT
21	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
21.1	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL
21.2	EKKE	ETHNIKO KENTRO KOINONIKON EREVNON	EL
22	e-helse	DIREKTORAT FOR E-HELSE	NO
23	U.PORTO	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	PT
24	SPMS	SERVICOS PARTILHADOS DO MINISTERIO DA SAUDE EPE	PT
25	NIJZ	NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE	SI
26	ERASMUS MC	ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	NL
27	EDHA	EUROPEAN DIGITAL HEALTH ACADEMY GGMBH	DE
28	HDR UK	HEALTH DATA RESEARCH UK	UK
29	UESSEX	UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX	UK
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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

Developing a data quality and utility label for the European Health Data Space.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
DQ&U	Data Quality & Utility
HDAB	Health Data Access Bodies

1. Introduction

1.1. Definition of Task 4.1.

This deliverable corresponds to the QUANTUM EU project deliverable 4.1, the outcome of Task 4.1: Capacity needs assessment. The definition of Task 4.1 is:

This task will engage with data holders, health data access bodies, data users and evidence decision-making stakeholders, in order to explain the expectations on each of them for creating or making use of the QUANTUM label. Health data access bodies will be interested in how to supervise and certify data quality labels, data holders on how to get into the maximum level of excellence in quality, and, end-users about data quality methods and tools to get the most out of data. This task will collate gaps from these different stakeholders in their workforce skills, organisational practices, data management pipelines and decision-making pathways. From this it will formulate an educational needs' assessment, stakeholder specific syllabus for online educational courses and an inventory of complementary guidance material that would help them to implement the smooth and efficient incorporation of QUANTUM, to be used by Task 5.3. Importantly, the analysis of gaps will take into account the gender perspective.

This task will develop the educational material to guide stakeholders in completing (i.e., filling out and finalizing) and utilising the data quality and utility label.

1.2. EHDS and data quality

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation will heavily impact the way we manage health data. Hence, instruments to ensure data quality are important in the implementation of the regulation. The importance of data quality is emphasised in the EHDS regulation in both the recitals and several core chapters.

In chapter III, which addresses electronic health record (EHR) systems, the term “EHRs” is used to broadly encompass more than just hospital systems. Article 23 of this chapter stipulates that the common specifications for EHRs must include requirements related to data quality. However, the regulation does not provide explicit details on what these data quality requirements entail, leaving room for further clarification and development.

Chapter IV, which focuses on the secondary use of health data, provides more concrete guidance on data quality in section 5. Article 56 introduces the concept of a “data quality and utility label”, offering a framework for assessing and communicating the quality and usefulness of health data. This label is intended to serve as a critical tool for stakeholders, ensuring that data used for secondary purposes meets established quality standards, thereby fostering trust.

The health data to be administered under the EHDS is planned to include health records, clinical trials, pathogens, health claims and reimbursements, genetic data, public health registry information, wellness data and information on healthcare resources, expenditure and financing. Article 33 of the EHDS regulation further expands on the scope of data categories, addressing additional types of health-related data to ensure comprehensive coverage. The rich spectrum of health data, ranging in complexity and format, requires knowledge and training from data users, data holders, and health data access bodies to enable them to interpret the data quality and utility effectively.

1.3. Scope of deliverable

This deliverable focuses on the educational requirements essential for implementing the data quality and utility label within the EHDS framework. Specifically, it outlines a curriculum tailored to the needs of data users, data holders, and health data access bodies, providing them with the knowledge and skills required to understand, apply, and benefit from the label.

This deliverable thus serves as a foundational step in the capacity-building efforts under Task 4.1, ensuring that stakeholders are equipped to use and implement the label effectively and sustainably.

2. Needs assessment

The outcome of this deliverable is to build on top of findings in milestone 4.1. This milestone presents survey results focused on identifying stakeholders, assessing current skills related to data quality, and implementing data quality tools and labelling. It offers a detailed analysis of the current landscape and highlights the urgent training and educational needs within the health data ecosystem. The summary below provides an overview of the key findings and implications from milestone 4.1. However, it is important to note that the milestone itself is an extensive document, offering a more detailed and in-depth analysis of the survey results ([see in appendix 1](#)).

Stakeholder identification revealed the involvement of a diverse array of participants from multiple countries, underscoring the widespread interest and necessity for robust data quality mechanisms.

The skills' assessment indicated considerable engagement with data quality issues, but it also highlights a notable variation in the expertise and understanding of health data quality principles among stakeholders. This underscores the urgent need for tailored educational programs and resources to elevate overall competency in data management and quality assurance.

Moreover, the development of a data quality labelling system is set to transform how health data is perceived and utilised within the sector. Initial feedback on this labelling process

showed strong support for its importance, though it also identified areas needing improvement in its application and effectiveness (e.g. stakeholder skills and knowledge, organisational structures and processes...).

The survey also highlighted a broader educational need encompassing all critical aspects of data quality management. Addressing this need is essential for fostering a comprehensive understanding of data quality principles among stakeholders. However, this particular deliverable will concentrate only on developing educational materials related to understanding, using, and implementing the data quality label mechanism.

3. Deliverable inputs

This deliverable is developed based on two primary sources of input within the QUANTUM project, specifically selected to inform the creation of training materials that address the Data Quality & Utility (DQ&U) label specifications, methodology, and application processes.

1. Stakeholder-Identified Needs from the Gap Analysis (Milestone 4.1):

The gap analysis conducted in milestone 4.1, from March 21 to April 30, gathered input directly from stakeholders to identify specific educational needs for effectively implementing, and using the DQ&U label. These insights have shaped the curriculum to ensure it directly addresses the challenges faced by data users, data holders, and health data access bodies as they interact with the QUANTUM label.

2. Relevant QUANTUM Deliverables and Milestones:

Several deliverables and milestones within the QUANTUM project provide foundational information on the DQ&U label specifications, scoring system, and data holder maturity model. Although some of these deliverables and milestones are still in development, they outline essential concepts and frameworks that are relevant for the training materials in this deliverable. Key inputs include:

- **Deliverable 1.1:** Specification of the data sets' quality and utility label (m9)
- **Deliverable 1.2:** Specification for the assessment of data holders' maturity model (m9)
- **Milestone 2.1:** Landscape analysis with recommendations for the design of the DQ&U label (m3)
- **Deliverable 2.1:** Initial release of the QUANTUM tool in Zenodo (Version 1.0 beta) and GitHub (m20)
- **Deliverable 3.1:** Assessment report on the implementation process (m25)
- **Deliverable 3.2:** Guidelines for the implementation of the labelling mechanism as referenced in Article 56 of the HealthData@EU legislative proposal (m26)

These inputs provide a framework for the curriculum, focusing on the DQ&U label's structure,

methodology, scoring system, and practical application. They guide the development of training materials that will support stakeholders in accurately completing, understanding, and utilising the label to enhance the quality and utility of health data.

By aligning the curriculum with these targeted insights, the deliverable is designed to equip stakeholders with the precise knowledge and tools necessary to implement and sustain the DQ&U label within the EHDS framework.

The Quantum Academy will focus on distinct educational content tailored to its objectives, excluding topics related to improving data quality and maturity at data holders' sites. These areas are specifically addressed by the "Capacity Building on Primary Use of Health Data" initiative (HADEA/2022/OP/0006), which concentrates on enhancing data quality for primary data sources.

For the training provided to Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), the QUANTUM Academy will clarify its alignment and complementarity with the "Capacity Building for Secondary Use of Health Data" project (HADEA/2023/OP/0024), which targets broader data quality training needs. This approach ensures that learners understand how QUANTUM integrates with these broader capacity-building efforts.

To maximise efficiency and coherence, partner i~HD, leading the development of educational content for both the Capacity Building project and QUANTUM, will take measures to avoid duplication of efforts across these initiatives.

4. Educational platform

The training and educational resources developed under the QUANTUM project will primarily be hosted on the i~HD Academy, operated by the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data. Participants will gain access to training that aligns with QUANTUM's goals and outcomes, ensuring a structured learning experience.

In addition, the QUANTUM Academy on the [project's official webpage](#) will provide supplementary information, updates, and resources to support stakeholders in engaging with the QUANTUM project's outputs.

To further broaden access, key training resources will also be made available through the European Health Information Portal. This ensures that stakeholders across the EU can easily locate and utilise the educational materials, enhancing visibility and reach.

5. QUANTUM Academy Curriculum

5.1. Overview

The development of the QUANTUM educational curriculum will follow a structured approach,

organised into multiple modules, each focusing on a specific area of data quality knowledge. Each module will consist of several chapters, with each chapter containing multiple learning objects. These learning objects will be designed to cover the essential topics and subtopics within the chapter, employing various formats such as videos, interactive tutorials, and case studies to enhance the learning experience. At the end of each chapter, learners will be assessed through quizzes or other assessment methods to ensure they have grasped the key concepts. This curriculum structure aims to provide a robust and engaging educational experience for participants.

Structure	Requirements	Description
Module	Module title	
	Learning objective	A brief description of what learners should achieve by the end of the module.
Chapter	Chapter title	
	Learning objective	Each chapter contains one or more learning objects designed to cover different subtopics of the chapter's main topic.
Learning object	Learning outcome	Indicating the method used to assess the understanding of the chapter's key concepts (e.g., quiz, assignment, project...).
	Object title	
	Object description	A brief description of the content and purpose of the learning object.
	Object format	The type of the learning object (e.g., video, PDF document, infographic...).

5.2. Intended users

This deliverable and curriculum target the following stakeholders as outlined in the grant agreement.

Data holder

Data holders are responsible for implementing measures to assess and publish the quality and utility of the datasets, and provide information about the maturity of their data quality management procedures through the use of a DQ&U label. Importantly, data holders are required to provide a DQ&U label specifically for datasets containing electronic health data that have been collected and processed with the support of Union or national public funding, in accordance with the elements outlined in paragraph 3 of the EHDS regulation.

The QUANTUM Academy will provide educational materials specifically tailored to help data holders understand how to implement, apply, and assess this label. This training will guide data holders in understanding the requirements needed for a dataset to meet the standards for secondary use of health data within the EHDS.

Data users

Data users, who are the direct beneficiaries of access to high-quality datasets, include a range of stakeholders (e.g. researchers, public bodies, policymakers...) and even the data collectors themselves. The QUANTUM Academy will provide these stakeholders with educational materials targeted to help them understand and effectively interpret the data quality and utility label. This will empower data users to make informed decisions and maximise the benefits of the high-quality data available within the EHDS. Additionally, at a later stage, data users will have the opportunity to provide feedback on how well a dataset fits their specific purposes (e.g., research queries). This will further enhance the continuous improvement of data offerings by ensuring datasets meet user needs.

Health Data Access Bodies (HDAB)

HDABs are central to the accurate and consistent implementation of the data quality and utility (DQ&U) label, with the goal of continuously enhancing the quality of datasets available through HealthData@EU. HDABs will be responsible not only for overseeing the DQ&U label's application, but also for hosting the necessary forms and tools that data holders will use to fill in and manage the label. This includes providing a dedicated platform and support services to assist data holders in accurately completing the labelling process.

To fulfil these responsibilities effectively, HDABs will receive targeted training through the QUANTUM Academy. This training will cover their role in supporting data holders, managing the DQ&U tool, and ensuring alignment with the requirements of HealthData@EU.

5.3. The structure of the curriculum

The QUANTUM Academy is designed to equip stakeholders with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively implement and utilise the data quality, utility, and maturity label. Each of the modules and chapters will be developed in detail when preparing the educational materials, making clearer who are the main recipients of the contents.

Summary

	Chapters	HDAB	Data Holders	Data users
Module 1	Introduction	xxx	xxx	xxx
	1. Specification of the D&Q label	xxx	xxx	xxx

Module 2	2 Data holders' maturity model	xx	xxx	x
	3. Fit-for-purpose (users' experience)	x	xx	xxx
Module 3	1. Tools and methodology available	xx	xxx	x
	2. Design and development of the label tool	xx	xxx	x
	3. Implementing and interpreting the label	xx	xx	xxx
	4. Interaction with the label from the HDAB	xxx	xx	x

Note: the number of "x" represents what stakeholder would be benefiting the most out of the programme.

Module 1: Introduction

Overview

Data quality is a critical component of the health ecosystem, influencing research outcomes, patient care, and policy decisions. This introductory module lays the foundation for understanding the significance of data quality utility and maturity and the role of the QUANTUM project, within the EHDS.

This, **Introduction to Health Data Quality**, provides a broad overview of data quality, introducing key concepts and real-world examples that underscore its importance in the health sector

Learning outcomes

Each chapter concludes with a multiple-choice quiz designed to assess the learner's understanding of the key concepts covered.

Learning objectives

- Importance of Data Quality

Understand the significance and complexity of data quality in health data and its impact specific towards primary and secondary use cases (e.g., research, policymaking...).

- Defining Data Quality

Explore how data quality is defined across different frameworks and into data quality dimensions.

- Data life cycle

Explore the stages of the data life cycle and their relevance to data quality and utility. Learn how each stage impacts overall data quality and how these considerations are integrated into the labelling process.

- **Primary and Secondary Use of Health Data**
Grasp the implications of data quality in both primary and secondary contexts, with examples highlighting its critical role.
- **Current State of Data Quality**
Analyse current practices, challenges, and gaps in data quality within the health ecosystem.
- **Stakeholder Roles**
Identify key stakeholders involved in data quality and understand their responsibilities and interactions within the health data ecosystem.
- **EHDS and Data Quality Requirements**
Gain a clear understanding of the EHDS, its data quality standards, and the implications for health data across Europe.

Module 2: Data Quality Components in QUANTUM

Overview

This module delves into specific components of data quality within the QUANTUM project. It is structured to provide learners with a thorough understanding of the elements necessary to create and apply the quality and utility label.

This module contains three chapters:

- **Chapter 1: Specifications of the Quality and Utility Label**
Explores the design, criteria, and metrics that define the quality and utility label in QUANTUM
- **Chapter 2: Data Holders' Maturity Model**
Provides insights into the data holders' maturity model, which assesses and enhances data quality management practices.
- **Chapter 3: Fit for Purpose (Users' experience)**
Focuses on how data users assess whether a dataset meets their specific needs or research queries.

Learning outcomes

Each chapter concludes with a multiple-choice quiz designed to assess the understanding of the key concepts covered.

Chapter 1: Specifications of the Quality and Utility Label

Learning objectives

- Data Quality Framework and Dimensions
Understand which data quality dimensions have been used to create the label specification and how these dimensions are defined.
- Label Design
Understand the methodology behind the construction of the quality and utility label, including criteria selection and indicator weighting.
- Aggregation and Acceptability Levels
Learn how dimensions scores are aggregated to form a comprehensive label and establish a minimum threshold for acceptability.
- Implementation Strategies
Explore strategies for implementing the quality and utility label, challenges, best practices, and the importance of continuous improvement.

Chapter 2: Data Holders' Maturity Model

Learning objectives

- Definition and Purpose
Understand what a data maturity model is, its benefits, and its impact on data quality and utility labelling.
- Data quality management
Understand the principles of health data quality management within the context of the QUANTUM data quality and utility label, focusing on key objectives and best practices for aligning with regulatory standards.
- Maturity Model Levels
Learn about the different levels of the data holder's maturity model in QUANTUM, covering key dimensions such as data management governance, data access, and analytics environment.
- Implementation strategies
Explore strategies for implementing the maturity model, challenges, best practices, and the importance of continuous improvement in data management.

Chapter 3: Fit for Purpose (Users' Experience)

Learning objectives

- Understanding 'fit for purpose' and 'fit for use' concepts

Understand the concepts of 'fit for purpose' and 'fit for use' in the context of health data quality. Exploring how these terms differ and how these concepts are represented in the data quality and utility label to communicate a dataset's usability across diverse applications.

- User-centric data quality assessment

Explore how data users evaluate a dataset's quality based on specific goals and requirements. Gain insight into the assessment methodology for determining fit-for-purpose, which ensures that the data meets the expectations outlined in the data quality and utility label.

Module 3: Understanding of the Label

Overview

This module focuses on the assessment of the label, providing a comprehensive understanding of the tools, methodologies, design, development, and implementation processes. This module contains four chapters:

- **Chapter 1: Tools and Methodologies available**

Provides an overview of existing technologies and methodologies for measuring data quality in the health data ecosystem.

- **Chapter 2: Design and Development of the Label Tool**

Explains the iterative process involved in designing and developing the QUANTUM label tool.

- **Chapter 3: Implementing and Interpreting the Label**

Demonstrates how to interpret the tool and utilise it in the decision-making.

- **Chapter 4: Interaction with the label from the HDAB Perspective**

Examines how HDABs interact with the label to ensure high-quality and utility standards for secondary data use.

Learning outcomes

Each chapter concludes with a multiple-choice quiz designed to assess the understanding of the key concepts covered.

Chapter 1: Tools and Methodology available

Learning Objectives

- **Methodology Behind the DQ&U Label Specifications**
Gain insight into the methodology that guided the development of the Data Quality and Utility (DQ&U) label specifications. Learn about the key requirements and criteria that influenced the selection of specific tools and metrics within the QUANTUM project to ensure alignment with EHDS goals.
- **Development and Functionality of the DQ&U Label Tool**
Understand the structure and functionality of the DQ&U label tool, including how it captures, scores, and reports on data quality metrics. Explore the technical aspects of the tool, including its integration with the HealthDCAT-AP metadata standard, to ensure standardised and interoperable metadata across datasets.
- **Visualisation and Presentation of Data Quality Scores**
Learn how data quality scores are visualised and made accessible on metadata records within the QUANTUM framework. This section includes examples and case studies illustrating how data quality metrics are displayed, providing users with clear, actionable insights that align with the DQ&U label specifications.

Chapter 2: Design and development of the label tool

Learning objectives

- **Rationale Behind the Design**
Understand the foundational reasoning and objectives that shaped the development of the data quality and utility label tool.
- **Iterative Development Process**
Gain insights into the iterative design approach, including criteria and indicator refinement leading to the final tool.
- **Presentation of the Final Tool**
Explore the structure, features, and functionalities of the completed data quality and utility label tool.

Chapter 3: Implementing and Interpreting the Label

Learning objectives

- **Understanding the implementation process**
Gain a clear overview of the step-by-step process for implementing the label tool, from initial

setup to integration within their usual data management workflow. This section will include guidelines on getting the required information into the assessment tool.

- Training and support for data holders

This will provide support resources available for data holders, including how to access these resources and the types of assistance provided. This chapter will cover the skills and knowledge data holders need to effectively utilise the label.

- Addressing common implementation challenges

Explore common challenges faced by data holders during the implementation of the label. Gain insight into best practices and solutions to overcome these obstacles, ensuring a smoother adoption process.

- Effective Use of the Label

Learn how to use and interpret the data quality and utility label effectively, with case studies illustrating its impact on workflow and decision-making.

- Fit-for-Purpose Assessment

Using some specific case-studies, understand how to determine if datasets are fit-for-use and how to improve them to anticipate fit-for-purpose (user's experience).

Chapter 4: Interaction with the Label from the HDAB Perspective

Learning objectives

- Interpreting the Label from the HDAB perspective

Understand how HDABs can interpret the label to assess data quality and utility in the context of facilitating secondary data use.

- Supervision and Governance of the Label

Gain an understanding of the supervisory role HDABs play in monitoring the label's integrity, ensuring that datasets meet the required quality and utility standards.

- Label Maintenance and Updates

Learn about the processes for updating and maintaining the label, including mechanisms for periodic review, stakeholder feedback integration, and alignment with evolving standards and technologies.

6. Next steps

The curriculum of the QUANTUM Academy is designed to align with the needs of its intended users, ensuring that stakeholders receive a targeted education on implementing and applying the data quality and utility label within HealthData@EU. The development of the modules outlined in this deliverable represents the immediate next steps in the QUANTUM educational curriculum. The focus will be on creating detailed content, tailored to the three main types of users, for each module, chapter, and learning object.

It will be essential to maintain close coordination with all other work packages within the QUANTUM project. This collaboration will ensure that the content will remain aligned with the latest developments and findings from other relevant work packages. Regular updates and reviews will be conducted to capture any changes in project deliverables that might impact the curriculum content.

Before the full rollout of the curriculum, the developed modules will undergo pilot testing with a selected group of stakeholders who will give feedback from the course material, texts, layout etc. We will then aim to make sure that the curriculum considers all kinds of learners and that it isn't gender-biased. Feedback from this pilot phase will be invaluable in refining the content and delivery methods to better meet the needs of the target audience. And once the content has been developed, reviewed, and refined based on the feedback, it will be finalised and uploaded to the QUANTUM Academy platform. A communication plan will be implemented to inform all stakeholders about the availability of the new educational resources.

Appendix 1

QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

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3.3	CHU Bordeaux	CHU HOPITAUX DE BORDEAUX	FR
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5	UCSC	UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE	IT
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12	AP-HP	ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HOPITAUX DE PARIS	FR
13	VIB	VIB VZW	BE
14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
15	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI
16	THL	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	FI
17	ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	FR
18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
20	ISS	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA	IT
21	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
21.1	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL
21.2	EKKE	ETHNIKO KENTRO KOINONIKON EREVNON	EL
22	e-helse	DIREKTORAT FOR E-HELSE	NO
23	U.PORTO	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	PT
24	SPMS	SERVICOS PARTILHADOS DO MINISTERIO DA SAUDE EPE	PT
25	NIJZ	NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE	SI
26	ERASMUS MC	ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	NL
27	EDHA	EUROPEAN DIGITAL HEALTH ACADEMY GGMBH	DE
28	HDR UK	HEALTH DATA RESEARCH UK	UK
29	UESSEX	UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX	UK
30	INSERM	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTE ET DE LA RECHERCHE MEDICALE	FR

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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

Developing a data quality and utility label for the European Health Data Space.

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1 Stakeholder identification

1.1 Overview of participating stakeholders

The survey successfully gathered 64 responses from a diverse cross-section of participants spread across various countries, demonstrating a broad interest and engagement in the topic matter. With Croatia leading in response rates, followed closely by Belgium and Italy, the survey data indicates a high level of participation across Europe, suggesting a keen interest in health data quality.

Participants included a mix of individuals with different roles within the health data ecosystem, encompassing data holders, data users, and data access bodies. The survey attracted 15 unique data holders who exclusively indicated to manage data without overlapping into usage or access body roles, highlighting a dedicated segment of stakeholders focusing on data control. Similarly, four unique data users were identified, indicating a specialised group that primarily leverages data for various applications without involvement in its control or distribution.

The presence of 5 data access bodies underscores the existence of dedicated stakeholders facilitating data availability, crucial for maintaining a fluid data exchange environment. Notably, 13 entities played multiple roles, engaging in holding, using, and controlling access to data. This multifunctionality suggests a highly integrated approach among certain stakeholders, likely enhancing the efficiency and dynamics within the health data ecosystem.

This diverse participation from various countries and multifaceted roles of the stakeholders provides valuable insights into the global and operational landscape of the data-related fields, offering a rich foundation for analysing the survey results and understanding the broader implications of the study.

4 participants indicated they don't see themselves as a data holder, data access body, or data user. These were patient representatives or health data consultants.

The annex offers a detailed view of the participating organisations and the specific roles within these organisations, segmented by country.

1.2 Stakeholder interaction with health data

The survey results highlight critical insights into the frequency of stakeholder interactions with health data, the importance of data quality in decision-making, and the impact of data quality issues on operational and analytical tasks. These findings emphasise the pervasive role that health data plays in the daily activities of the majority of respondents, and the significant reliance on data quality for effective decision-making and operational efficiency.

Frequency of interaction with health data

A significant majority of the respondents (81.81%) interact with health data at least weekly, with more than half (56.25%) engaging with it daily. This underscores the integral role health data plays in the routine operations of most stakeholders involved in health care and research sectors.

How frequently do you interact with health data in your role?	Percentage
Never (I do not interact with health data at all)	4.69 %
Rarely (once a month)	4.69 %
Sometimes (a few times a month)	7.81 %
Regularly (weekly)	25.56 %
Very frequently (daily)	56.25 %

Data quality is crucial for the majority of stakeholders, with over 84% indicating that the quality of data is moderately to absolutely critical in their decision-making process. This demonstrates a high dependency on robust data quality to support informed and accurate decisions.

How critical is health data quality in your decision-making process?	Percentage
Not at all critical (I can make decisions without considering data quality)	4.69 %
Slightly critical (data quality is a minor factor in my decision-making)	10.94 %
Moderately critical (data quality regularly influences my decisions)	34.38 %
Very critical (my decisions heavily rely on high-quality data)	31.25 %
Absolutely critical (I cannot make decisions without ensuring data quality first)	18.75 %

Impact of data quality issues

Despite the critical need for high-quality data, there are substantial challenges reported by respondents concerning data quality. A vast majority (87.5%) experience issues with data quality affecting their effectiveness, sometimes too very frequently. These challenges not only highlight the prevalence of data quality problems but also signify the profound impact such issues have on the effectiveness of data utilisation in operational and analytical capacities.

How often does poor data quality limit your effectiveness in utilising health data for your operational or analytical tasks?	Percentage
Never (it does not limit my effectiveness)	4.69 %
Rarely (it rarely poses minor issues)	7.81 %
Sometimes (sometimes issues, but manageable)	42.19 %
Regularly (frequent issues, significant affect my task)	40.63 %
Very frequently (consistent limits my effectiveness)	4.69 %

The challenges faced in managing health data are diverse and impact various aspects of data quality. Here's a summary of the most common challenges participants are facing.

- Poor data quality related to dimensions
 - Many participants encounter issues with inaccurate, incomplete, or inconsistent data.
 - Data often arrives with significant delays, which affects the accuracy and timeliness of reporting and subsequent decision-making processes.
 - This also includes unstructured data, incorrect annotations, and lack of logical control during data entry, leading to frequent errors and a lack of reliability.
- Lack of standardisation and coordination
 - There is a significant variation in how data is handled across different sites and services due to the absence of standardised practices, terminologies, and data dictionaries.
 - This lack of uniform standards complicates data integration and analysis.
- Documentation and metadata deficiencies
 - Inadequate documentation and metadata make it challenging to understand the data's context and to ensure its correct usage.
 - Many datasets lack comprehensive cohort descriptions, data dictionaries, and clear metadata explaining the data's logic and purpose.
- Data accessibility and sharing issues
 - Difficulties in linking data to the correct patient and venue, combined with primarily paper-based records and unstandardised formats, hinder efficient data sharing and accessibility.
 - This affects collaborations and limits the effectiveness of health data usage in research and clinical settings.
- Technology and resource limitations
 - Many systems still rely on outdated technology or manual processes, leading to delays and increased error rates.
 - There's also a frequent mention of insufficient resources for proper data quality control and the need for repeated data entry, which increases the likelihood of mistakes.
- Regulatory and privacy concerns
 - Ensuring data privacy and meeting compliance requirements are major challenges, especially when managing sensitive health data.

- These issues require meticulous processes to anonymise and secure data, which can be resource-intensive.

Difference among stakeholders

When dealing with health data, differences emerged among the three different stakeholders. Data access bodies reported the highest frequency of daily interactions with health data, underscoring their critical role in managing and facilitating data flows. In contrast, data holders and data users showed more variability in the frequency of their interactions, with results engaging with data on a weekly basis.

When it comes to the impact of poor data quality on their work, all groups reported significant challenges, but the effects varied by role. Data access bodies were most likely to report that poor data quality very frequently limits their effectiveness, highlighting the crucial importance of data quality in their operations. Data holders and data users also faced frequent issues, however, a larger proportion of data holders found these issues to be manageable compared to data users, who more often reported operational impacts like data access bodies.

The criticality of data quality in decision-making processes also varied, with data access bodies most likely to view data quality as very critical, indicating a high dependency on accurate and reliable data for making informed decisions. Data holders displayed the broadest range of responses regarding how critical data quality is to their decision-making, reflecting diverse roles and reliance on data within this group. Data users generally placed a high emphasis on data quality, although less uniformly than data access bodies, suggesting variations in how data influences their analytical and operational tasks.

2 Current skills assessment

2.1 Stakeholder level

This part of the survey aimed to evaluate the current level of understanding and the practical challenges individual stakeholders face in maintaining data quality within the health data ecosystem. This is crucial for identifying key areas where further training and resources are needed to enhance data quality standards and practices at an individual level.

Understanding of Data Quality

The responses reveal a diverse range of expertise levels with data quality concepts among stakeholders. Participants could rate their understanding of the topic on a scale from 1 to 5 (1 being no to little understanding, and 5 expert on the topic). A significant portion of the stakeholders rate their understanding as moderate (32.81% rated themselves as 3). However, 26.29% of the survey participants scored themselves high (13.79% rated themselves as 4, and 12.5% rated themselves as a 5). A notable 9.38% acknowledge having a lower understanding (rating 2) on data quality. This indicates a need for targeted educational efforts to ensure a uniform level of expertise across all stakeholders.

A strong majority (79.69%) have had experience assessing the quality of health data sets, which suggests a practical engagement with data quality issues, though the depth of this experience could vary.

Acquisition of knowledge and skills

Stakeholders have acquired their knowledge and skills primarily through a variety of sources.

Format of acquiring knowledge and skills	Percentage
In-house training program	17.31 %
Organisational guidelines and documentation	27.88 %
External training courses or workshop	13.46 %
Master's degree in a relevant field	20.19 %
Other	21.15 %

Organisational guidelines and documentation (27.88%) and in-house training programs (17.31%) are prominent, highlighting the organisation's role in education. External training and advanced degrees account for a substantial 33.65%, suggesting reliance on external resources for comprehensive education in data quality.

Encountering and addressing data quality errors

The vast majority of stakeholders (87.5%) have encountered data quality errors, which underscores the ongoing challenges in the field. The most common issues stakeholders are facing relate to data quality dimensions (e.g., missing data, accuracy errors, duplicated data, inconsistency errors within datasets and across different data sources, ...). Additional challenges arise during the data annotation and the extract, transform, and load (ETL) processes, where a lack of transparency and insufficient documentation fail to provide necessary context and clarity.

Have you encountered data quality errors in your work?	Percentage
No	12.5 %
Yes	87.5 %

What are the main causes of data quality issues from the stakeholder perspective?

- Deficient standards and guidelines
 - Absence of comprehensive guidelines or best practices for data entry, ETL processes, and assessment methodologies.
 - Lack of clear instructions and regulations regarding data quality standards.
 - Insufficient guidelines, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), and strategic direction.
- Documentation and awareness gaps
 - Inadequate documentation on data quality problems and curation processes.
 - General lack of awareness about data quality importance and practices.
 - Missing validation checks during the data collection phase.
- Technical and resource limitations
 - Poor software tools that fail to meet data quality standards.
 - Lack of technical skills required for effective data quality assessments.
 - Insufficient time and resources allocated at the data collection phase, compounded by high workloads.
- System and process inconsistencies
 - Heterogeneity between different systems and organisations complicates data integration and quality control.
 - Excessive reliance on free text and manual input, prone to errors.
 - No robust top-down instructions to govern and manage data quality effectively.
- Cultural and contextual changes
 - Absence of a culture of standardised data collection processes in clinical practice, affecting data consistency.
 - Differences in data utility between primary and secondary phases, introducing complexities in maintaining data quality at the source.

And while stakeholders are often (37.5%) or sometimes (45.31%) able to resolve issues, there's a significant portion that only rarely (9.38%) or never (1.56%) effectively manage these problems. This could reflect gaps in skills or resources necessary for effective data quality management.

Skills gap

The survey identified several areas where stakeholders feel they lack adequate skills.

Skills	Percentage
Developing and applying data quality metrics	13.70 %
Data quality auditing and reporting	12.33 %
Metadata management and documentation	11.30 %
Training in relevant data quality standards	9.59 %
Utilisation of data quality improvement software	8.90 %
Advanced data analysis and interpretation	8.22 %
Implementation of data governance policies	7.19 %
Skills for communicating data quality issues to stakeholders	6.85 %
Data integration and consolidation methods	6.85 %
Data cleaning techniques	6.51 %
Knowledge of legal and regulatory requirements regarding health data	4.72 %
Data privacy and security measures	3.77 %

Data quality metrics and data quality auditing (26.03%) and metadata management (11.30%) are critical areas where stakeholders feel unprepared. There is a recognised need for training in data quality standards, use of improvement software, and advanced data analysis. This aligns with the types of errors reported and the challenges in resolving them.

Difference among stakeholders

Some results indicated a difference in answer options depending on stakeholder type. Data users and data access bodies indicated to have a higher understanding of data quality. These

stakeholders also indicated a higher frequency of resolving data quality issues effectively, which may be attributed to practical experience and ongoing interactions with data quality tools and processes.

Conclusion

The survey has highlighted the active engagement of stakeholders with data quality issues but has also uncovered gaps in their knowledge and skills, potentially causing data quality errors. Some recommendations for addressing these gaps.

- Tailored training programs

In light of the identified gaps, it is recommended to develop customised training modules that specifically focus on key areas such as data quality metrics, metadata management, and the utilisation of specialised software tools. These modules should cater to the varied skill levels within the organisation, ensuring that all stakeholders are equipped to handle their data responsibilities effectively.

- Enhance in-house training

Strengthening the existing organisational guidelines and documentation is crucial. This enhancement will ensure that all materials are comprehensive and easily accessible, supporting stakeholders in adhering to data quality standards consistently and efficiently.

- Continuous professional development

Encourage ongoing professional development by integrating external courses and workshops into the career development paths of individual stakeholders. This approach will help keep the team alert of evolving standards and new technologies in health data management, fostering a culture of continuous improvement, learning and adaptation.

2.2 Organisation level

This section presents an analysis of the data quality literacy across the organisation, providing insights into the structural setups for managing data quality, and assesses the tools employed for this purpose. The insights derived from this survey are crucial for identifying and addressing areas needing improvement and for reinforcing our data governance frameworks.

Assessment of data quality literacy within the organisation

The survey responses exhibit a spectrum of data quality literacy within the organisation. Low levels (Very low to low) representing 25.01% of responses, the significant segment underscores a critical area for immediate educational interventions to bridge knowledge gaps.

Moderate understanding of data quality dominates the responses with 43.79%, this level indicates a basic, yet incomplete, grasp of data quality principles among the majority of the workforce. It points to the need for advanced training to move beyond foundational knowledge. High proficiency (high to very high) comprises 31.26% of the responses, this encouraging statistic reveals a strong data quality acumen among a substantial part of the organisation. However, the goal remains to elevate the entire organisation to this level of proficiency to ensure uniformity in data handling and processing.

Data quality literacy	Percentage
Very low	3.13 %
Low	21.88 %
Moderate	43.79%
High	15.63 %
Very high	15.63 %

Data quality management structure

The survey findings reveal a significant concern regarding the formal structures for data quality management within an organisation. A substantial 68.75% of respondents report the absence of designated roles such as data quality managers or teams. This deficiency is likely contributing to inconsistencies and inefficiencies in our data handling processes, underscoring a critical area for organisational improvement.

The survey also sought to understand how clearly defined the roles and responsibilities for data quality management are within the organisation. Results indicate a concerning lack of clarity in these roles and responsibilities. Only 15.63% of respondents feel that these roles are 'very clear'. Conversely, the majority, at 56.52%, find them only 'somewhat clear', signalling room for improvement in the explicit definition of these roles and responsibilities. This notable lack of clear definitions could seriously hinder effective data management practices and impact overall data quality improvement.

Are roles and responsibilities for data quality management clearly defined within your organisation?	Percentage
No answer	4.69 %
Not at all clear	10.94 %
Not very clear	28.13 %
Somewhat clear	56.52 %
Yes, very clear	15.63 %

Has your organisation established a dedicated data quality	Percentage
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team or appointed a data quality manager?	
No, we have not	68.75 %
Yes, we have a data quality manager	12.5 %
Yes, we have a data quality team	14.06 %
Yes, we have both	4.69 %

Utilisation of data quality tools

Organisations utilise a diverse toolkit for data quality assessment. These tools cover everything from ad-hoc solutions for immediate problems to comprehensive frameworks like ISO standards and the HIQA data quality framework.

- Data quality frameworks and standards
 - HIQA data quality framework, Health Information and Quality Authority framework aimed at improving health information quality.
 - ISO 8000 and ISO 33020, international standards for data quality and process quality metrics.
 - EUROSTAT data quality assessment methods, tools and methods defined by the European Statistical System for assessing the quality of statistical data.
 - ADOPT - BBMRI framework, a framework focused on optimising the operability of biobank processes and data.
 - FAIR data assessment tools, tools designed to ensure data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Programming and scripting solutions
 - Using R packages for statistical computing and graphics that enhance data analysis (e.g., Dlooker).
 - Using Python scripts tailored to specific data quality issues, offering flexibility and powerful data manipulation capabilities.
 - Power BI, a suite of business analytics tools for data visualisation and sharing insights.
 - SQL and Open Refine tools used for data cleaning and transformation tasks.
 - WHO Tools (ANACOD), a World Health Organization tool for analysing cause of death data.
 - OMOP data quality checks used within the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership framework for ensuring the quality of observational healthcare data.
- Specific data quality techniques

- Capture-recapture methods, statistical methods used to estimate the completeness of data by comparing multiple datasets or lists.
- Percentage morphologically verified, a specific quality control measure for verifying data based on its morphological characteristics.
- Number of sources/notifications per case, a method to ensure data completeness by tracking the number of notifications or sources for each data entry.
- Death certificate only, a specific focus on the quality of mortality data derived from death certificates.

To conclude, organisations often use manual assessment/curation processes and ad-hoc solutions to maintain data quality. These methods present certain challenges, especially as we scale and share data across various sources. Furthermore, the reliance on ad-hoc solutions, while demonstrating flexibility, points to a broader issue within organisations and across organisations - a lack of a clear, cohesive data quality strategy.

How effective do you find your current data quality tools and processes in meeting your organisational data quality needs?	Percentage
No answer	14.06 %
Not effective at all	9.38 %
Slightly effective	17.19 %
Moderately effective	48.44 %
Very effective	10.94 %

However, a majority (65.63%) of respondents feel that the data quality tools are only moderate to slightly effective, suggesting an urgent need for reevaluation and enhancement of these tools to ensure they fully address the specific challenges of our health data environment.

Challenges in data quality management

Respondents identify maintaining completeness and consistency of datasets as the most important challenge, indicating potential issues in data integration and lifecycle management. The need for better training and continuous monitoring of data quality are also highlighted as critical areas where the organisation must focus, particularly to empower employees to handle data quality.

What aspects of data quality management do you find most challenging or lacking in your organisation?	Percentage
Maintaining the completeness of datasets	12.94 %
Achieving consistency of data across different systems	12.62 %
Training staff on data quality best practices	11.97 %
Monitoring data quality on an ongoing basis	11.97 %

Updating data in a timely manner to support current operations	11 %
Implementing effective data quality tools and technologies	10.68 %
Establishing clear data governance policies	9.71 %
Integrating new data sources without compromising data quality	8.41 %
Ensuring the correctness of data for informed decision-making	6.74 %
Identifying and resolving data duplication	4.21 %

Difference among stakeholders

Results of our survey have provided insights into how different stakeholders perceive various aspects of data quality management within the organisation. Data literacy across the organisation was perceived differently per stakeholder group. Data users and data holders typically viewed data literacy levels as ‘moderate’, compared to data access bodies which answered in general as ‘high’ organisational literacy.

The clarity of roles and responsibilities also varied notably. Data holders and data users who confirmed clearer governance structures perceived roles as somewhat clearer, whereas data access bodies showed a stark contrast between those with and without affirmative responses, indicating that clearer roles were much recognised by stakeholders who acknowledged established governance structures.

Regarding the effectiveness of data quality tools and processes, all groups most commonly described them as ‘Moderately effective’, with data users showing the least variation in their responses. This points to a uniform expectation of tool and process effectiveness that appears not fully satisfied.

3 Data quality labelling

Data quality labelling is a crucial practice that directly impacts the usability and reliability of datasets within and across organisations. This section explores the involvement of the survey participants in data labelling processes, their experiences with labelled data, and their perceptions of the importance and effectiveness of data quality labels.

Stakeholder involvement and experiences

A notable 62.5% of respondents have been involved in documenting or labelling the quality of datasets for use by others, indicating a significant engagement with this practice within the organisation. Conversely, the same percentage (62.5%) have not worked with datasets whose quality was previously assessed and labelled by others, suggesting potential gaps in the internal sharing and utilisation of quality assessments. Among those who have used such datasets, 23.44% found the labelled quality information helpful, while 14.06% reported that the information was not useful, highlighting areas for improvement in the labelling process to enhance its utility.

Have you been involved in documenting or labelling the quality of datasets for use by others?	Percentage
Yes	62.5 %
No	37.5 %

Have you worked with datasets whose quality was previously assessed and labelled by others?	Percentage
No	62.5 %
Yes, but the labelled quality information was not helpful	14.06 %
Yes, the labelled quality information was helpful	23.44 %

Perceived importance of data quality labelling

The majority of respondents recognise the importance of data quality labelling, with 68.79% considering it very important or essential. This consensus underscores the critical role that effective labelling plays in ensuring data integrity and supporting informed decision-making.

How important is the implementation of data quality labelling in your organisation?	Percentage
Not important	6.25 %
Slightly important	9.38 %
Moderately important	15.63 %
Very important	37.5 %
Essential	31.29 %

Expectations and essentials for effective data quality labels

What do you expect to be included in a data quality label?	Percentage
Indicators of data quality dimensions	28.86 %
Information related to the source of the data	25.87 %
Date of last update of the label	24.88 %
Data provenance information	20.40 %
Other items	Metadata requirements
	Assessment methods
	FAIR requirements

Visualisation of data quality labels

How would data quality labels be visualised for optimal usefulness?	Percentage
Colour-coded systems	27.59 %
Textual descriptions/tags	21.38 %
Badge or icon indicators	20 %
Interactive tools or hover-over information	17.93 %
Dashboard widgets	13.10 %

The survey results highlight a robust interest and involvement in data quality labelling among all stakeholders, coupled with a clear recognition of its importance for maintaining high standards of data quality. However, the mixed experiences with labelled data suggest a need for a transparent labelling process. By focusing on the content and visualisation of data labels, as well as ensuring their comprehensive application across all datasets, organisations can enhance the effectiveness of data quality labelling, thereby supporting better data usability and decision-making capabilities.

Difference among stakeholders

The results indicate that stakeholders, regardless of their specific roles, share remarkably similar views and experiences related to data quality labelling. This suggests a similar recognition of the importance of data quality labelling and similar levels of engagement with data labelling practices across different organisational roles. The consistency across different stakeholder groups might imply that data quality initiatives and policies are uniformly understood and applied within the organisation or health context in which this health data is derived.

4 Preferred learning formats

Understanding the preferred learning formats and related factors among our stakeholders is essential for designing effective data quality education programs. Our survey explores these preferences, revealing a diverse range of favoured learning methods and the amount of time individuals are willing to commit, along with the features they value most in learning programs.

Learning formats

The results show a close split among the top choices for learning formats, indicating a varied preference across respondents.

What format of learning do you prefer for data quality education?	Percentage
In-person workshop	23.98 %
Tutorials	23.39 %
Webinars	21.05 %
Self-paced online courses	19.88 %
Reading materials (e.g., academic articles, guidelines)	11.70 %

Time commitment

Our survey also investigated how much time participants are willing to dedicate to learning about data quality.

How much time are you willing to commit to data quality education per week?	Percentage
Less than 1 hour	18.18 %
1 to 2 hours	68.18 %
3 to 5 hours	13.64 %
6 to 10 hours	0 %
More than 10 hours	0 %

Important factors in learning programs

Participants prioritise various features in learning programs, which can guide the development of future training.

What factors are most important to you in a learning program for data quality?	Percentage
Schedule flexibility	21.86 %
Support and resources available post-completion	20.92 %
User-friendly program platform	18.41 %
Access to experts and tutors	16.74 %
Financial cost	12.09 %
Certification upon completion	10.23 %

Feedback underscores a preference for practical, hands-on approaches that not only integrate seamlessly into basic scientific education but are also adaptable to various experience levels. This indicates a strong demand for programs that not only teach theoretical concepts but also provide practical tools and techniques that can be immediately applied.

The diversity in preferred learning formats and the clear priorities for educational program

features reflect our organisation's need for flexible, practical, and accessible data quality education. These insights are invaluable for developing tailored training programs that align with stakeholder preferences and maximise learning outcomes, thereby enhancing overall data quality management capabilities.

5 Curriculum expectations

Critical topics in data quality curriculum

Our survey identifies several key areas that stakeholders find critical for inclusion in the data quality curriculum.

Which of the following topics do you find most critical in the data quality curriculum?	Percentage
Data quality measurements and metrics	16.46 %
Fundamentals of health data quality	14.94 %
Data quality improvement strategies	14.02 %
Data cleaning and validation techniques	13.72 %
Data governance and data quality stewardship	11.28 %
Implementation of data quality tools and software	10.98 %
Data quality visualisation techniques	10.06 %
Advanced data analysis and interpretation	8.54 %

Respondents also expressed a desire to see the curriculum expanded to cover additional topics and skills, including:

- Specialised data quality management approaches, tailored strategies for different types of data.
- The role of artificial intelligence, deeper dives into how AI can be leveraged to improve or potentially compromise data quality.
- Standards and accreditation, detailed discussions on how achieving high data quality can facilitate obtaining accreditations like ISO 20387 - General requirements for biobanking.

There is a strong preference for integrating real-world health data quality scenarios into the curriculum. This approach could help learners see practical applications of theoretical knowledge and understand the complexities of data quality in a healthcare setting. Case studies can provide valuable insights into common challenges and effective strategies for managing data quality.

Application of skills

Participants envision applying the skills acquired from the data quality curriculum in several impactful ways within their roles.

- Developing or improving data quality strategies, formulating or enhancing organisational strategies to better manage data quality.
- Enhancing data quality control and assurance procedures, applying learned skills to refine current processes throughout the data lifecycle, ensuring consistency and reliability of data.
- Understanding data collection mechanisms, gaining insights into different data collection methods and their impacts on data quality, which is crucial for making informed decisions about data handling practices.
- Supporting accreditation efforts, using improved data quality to meet the standards required for various accreditations, which can enhance the organisation's credibility and operational efficiency.

The curriculum expectations outlined by the respondents indicate a strong demand for a comprehensive, practical, and case-based learning experience that addresses both general and specific needs related to data quality. By incorporation of these elements, the proposed data quality curriculum will not only enhance individual competencies but also drive significant improvements in organisational data management practices.

6. Curriculum evaluation

For assessing the effect of the data quality training, the respondents preferred easily accessible methods, such as feedback forms and staff certificates. The more elaborate methods to estimate the achieved impact in the organisation, such as cost-benefit analysis, were not favoured.

How should the impact of training be measured in your organisation?	Percentage
Survey or feedback forms	28.59 %
Certification or accreditation of staff	23,57 %
Review of project outcomes or case studies	22.86 %
Pre-and post-training assessment	19.30 %
Cost-benefit analysis	5.72 %

7. Conclusion

The QUANTUM project represents a significant stride towards enhancing health data quality across Europe. This milestone, containing survey results, focused on stakeholder identification, current skills' assessment, and the implementation of data quality labelling, provides an analysis of the current landscape and the urgent needs within the health data ecosystem.

From the stakeholder identification, it is evident that a wide array of participants across multiple countries are involved and completed the survey. This diverse participation underscores the broad interest and necessity for robust data quality mechanisms. However, obtaining more results would have been beneficial and provided us with a more complete view of data quality skills and needs.

The skills' assessment reveals that while there is a considerable engagement with data quality issues, there is a notable variation in the level of expertise and understanding of health data quality principles among stakeholders. This highlights an urgent need for tailored educational programs and resources to elevate the overall competency in data management and quality assurance.

Furthermore, the development of a data quality labelling system is poised to revolutionise the way health data is perceived and utilised across the sector. The initial feedback on the data labelling process indicates a strong endorsement of its importance, yet also suggests areas for improvement in its application and effectiveness.